

THEORIZING URBAN TRANSFORMATION AND ADAPTATION IN KUMASI, GHANA: REFLECTIONS ON SOME OF THE FORCES SHAPING AN ORDINARY CITY

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Abstract

Advertising billboards in Kumasi are a reminder of the extent of the penetration of market forces in everyday life (commodification). The built environment is awash with signs and symbols, sending mixed messages and images of goods and services that promises a better life. These images seem oblivious to the lived experiences of the majority in Kumasi. While billboards serve primarily to promote goods and services, including religion, they also play an important role in diverting attention and focus from the drudgery of everyday real-lives of ordinary citizens by redirecting focus to sense gratification and aspiration. The main research question has to do with trying to understand the impact of commodification in this and similar cities in Africa as a contribution to African urbanism. There are also concerns about the impact of ethical implications about psychological effects of visual pollution and the constant bombarding of the senses. In Kumasi, such spaces also serve to entrench existing class distinction by providing an avenue for memorializing important individuals in society. This research stays on the surface as an analytical approach. It illustrates how we might interpret the surface more seriously in our analysis of the contemporary city in terms of the silences and reminders of past exclusionary colonial representations of the city. The research adopted random interviews with the inhabitants, traversing the city and field observations, and taking photos analogous to a flâneur. It is argued that the invisible city of the marginalized and poor seems to always make an unwelcome intrusion on such reserved spaces. Such invisible spaces also form an integral part of albeit unacknowledged cityscape of Kumasi and similar African cities. The aim of the research is twofold. It is to shine a spotlight on the coincidence of pervasive commodification – as a condition of modern life including spiritual malaise – and the rise of a media culture even in far-flung cities like Kumasi. Secondly, it is to make a broader contribution to urban studies and African urbanism in particular. It suggests the need to explore similar dynamics in other African cities with purpose to explore a decommodified human-centered African urbanism as part of the ‘right to the city’

Keywords: Postmodernism, Post-fordist, Postmodern Urbanism, Ordinary City, Flexible Economy, Kumasi.

Beautiful it was not. The Golden City was still too raw and drab and dirty for that.
But it was a real city, no one could deny that, and it was a homely place in its
fashion. (Pakenham, 1979)

1. INTRODUCTION

African cities are going through a tremendous process of transformation. The inherited colonial urban fabric is reshaped and transformed through a combination of innovation and adaptation using references from everywhere. Advertising billboards play a significant role as a conduit for displaying alternative lifestyles, goods, and services from here and elsewhere. As a result, the built environment in Kumasi is remarkably littered with advertising billboards along the main thoroughfares and around traffic circles. Buildings are also not immune to this seemingly

pervasive phenomenon of advertising as they are adorned with logos and popular local and but mainly foreign name brands.

The paper highlights the extent of the reach of economic globalism and the resultant penetration of market forces in all aspects of society, leaving no space untouched. The aim of the paper is to contribute to discussions about African urbanism. Kumasi seems to present a market-oriented approach that while similar to other Africa cities, has unique elements that are remarkable for a visitor.

The first part presents the city of Kumasi as a complex phenomenon that presents unique as well as common elements with other cities in Africa, urban decay, colonial urban fabric, pervasive informality, precarity, endemic traffic congestion, and resilience here understood as the balancing of mental, physical, social and spiritual aspects. In spite of these seemingly immense challenges, these cities continue to be recipients of unprecedented levels of urbanization and hope for a better life. The argument being here is that such cities on the margins of the global economies have much to contribute in African urban futures and debates about African urbanism.

The rise in consumerism and preoccupation with visual consumption and advertising as symptomatic of global forces at play in far-flung cities like Kumasi is also discussed. This is aided by a penchant with the urban spectacle as embodied in big infrastructure projects such as shopping atria (Kumasi Mall), airport improvements (Prempeh I International Airport), and the Pokuase, Asafo and Sofoline Interchanges. These are key infrastructure elements that Robinson's (2002) 'off the map' cities like Kumasi, which aspire to be global cities (see Sassen 1991, Kearney 2024 among others)) must acquire.

Part of the discussion is how such cities are linked to the global economy albeit as consumers of mass-produced goods and services. Predominant narratives about the city as depicted on billboards center around mainly consumption. It would appear that the city lacks the ability to offer prospects of improving the lives of the urban poor – yet remain central to keeping hope alive for a better tomorrow.

The second section attempts to read the city as a much more complex environment than depicted on billboards by highlighting the underlying class and ethnic divisions, as evidenced the billboards celebrating the death of certain individuals, a costly undertaking for multitude and a mark of class division. The last section reflects on the penchant for partial representations of the city and the need for calculating more inclusionary urban visions, beginning with paying attention to the present as a process of something emerging.

2. RE-PRESENTING THE CITY

Kumasi city is peppered with texts. Such forms of self-representation through advertising billboards perpetuate past exclusionary visions and as such marginalize others marked by class and ethnicity. The majority of products displayed on the billboards for example tend to be foreign products that bear little resemblance to the multitudes of inhabitants of Oseikrom.

The class element is manifested through funeral announcements on major intersections such as Ahodwo and Santasi roundabouts. These billboards sit side-by-side with those advertising goods. A chance encounter and conversation with a local informs that billboards cost advertising costs \$1000 for a period of 2 weeks. Social status could not be more vividly displayed in a city where most majority of citizens lead precarious lives in the overcrowded informal market, itself saturated with used and twice discarded goods and trinkets from elsewhere.

Their forms are but moments in Kumasi's transient history, part of a long process of remaking the city using fragments and references from elsewhere, a process that is by no means unique to Kumasi (see for example Watson 2014; Bahn 2001).

Such images are contradictory and provisional and may require interpretation by the author to be fully understood for their meaning and symbolism. They constitute a unitary and partial view of the city, a yearning inasmuch as it is denial and/or inability to fashion a vision that captures the complexity that is the city.

This might include for example advertising that serve local business or reflect indigenous cultural adaptations rather than merely foreign consumerism. Admittedly, the thirst for foreign investment and lust fashionable brands might too much to resist

The current urban fabric betrays Kumasi's colonial past upon whose ruins a new urban form is emerging haltingly as it were, through an innovative combination of recycling, re- adapting, and continuity with billboards providing a snapshot of this unfolding urban drama. Re-presenting the city is therefore always going to be a partial endeavor as the city unfolds and morphs. The metaphoric reference to Kumasi as a garden city, largely as a consequence of the lush vegetation, represents yet another partial attempt at re-presenting the image of Kumasi as city. Collins (2014) notes the following in reference to Kumasi as a garden city:

Kumasi has lost most of its green vegetation to housing developments and commercial activities. The city's preserved green belts have become vacant, most of the parks and gardens are no more with many of the remaining parks converted into commercial centres. Urban sprawl was also very prevalent causing excessive loss of green vegetation at the fringes of the city. Kumasi now lacks enough green vegetation which is contrary to the garden city model that the city was built on

In the context of a coincidence in commodification and the dominance of media culture, billboards provide a rather unique avenue at this selective visioning process. This seemingly relentless selective imaging of Kumasi highlights the recurrent theme of inequality and class dimension of urban agendas.

In the redevelopment of New York city, Robert Moses took a leaf out of Baron Hausmann approach in the renovation of Paris almost a century earlier. Working class areas were destroyed to make way for their unitary visions of their cities.

In Zimbabwe, operation murambatsvina (restore order) was another singular vision that resulted in 700,000 people's homes destroyed or left without a livelihood? Men, women, children were made homeless.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study is a phenomenological case study. Data was collected through observation and conversation (embodied encounters) with some of the inhabitants encountered on the streets. Phenomenology is an inquiry which is based on scenes, scenarios, events as perceived by the researcher (subjective interpretation), in this case myself. Kumasi was my case. The photographs were the main impetus behind the research, they informed the narrative. This was supplemented with media posts and social media in an endeavor to present a more rounded portrayal for Kumasi as a lived and evolving city.

The researcher's experiences in Kumasi inform the design and presentation of the realities I observed as I strolled down the streets of Kumasi. The aim was to capture the 'essence' of Kumasi's evolving urban fabric as a result of public and private interventions. Other sources of data include print and mainly social media in order to portray the city as an encounter, lived and constantly evolving entity.

I walked through the streets of Kumasi, with amazement, excitement and a sense of wonder and curiosity as a flâneur would. The latter is a French noun that more or less translates kind of urban explorer. Their goal is to take in city life. The flâneur is both a spectator, as well as an urban detective of sorts, responsible for hanging out and surveying the changing nature of city life. The flâneur is also a reminder that city life is indeed a kind of spectacle. When the flâneur figure was coming into its own, Paris was going through a profound transformation with Baron Haussmann's transformation of Paris in the mid nineteenth century.

The essay draws inspiration from a body of scholarship on the city, criticisms notwithstanding, which tries to draw the city's inventiveness and parodies, and draw attention to neglected spaces and figures in the city. de Certeau (1984) posits that the city reveals itself through walking and cannot be summarized. Walter Benjamin ([1982] 2000) figure of the flâneur invites us to 'read the city from its street-level intimations', to encounter the city as a complex lived phenomenon, and to seek alternative accounts/storylines based on wondering.

Zygmunt Bauman (1996) introduces other figures in the city in addition to the flâneur; the city of the vagrant/vagabond, and the commuter among others. My ambiguous status as a regular visitor meant that I could still wonder about the city as a tourist would albeit with some sense of familiarity with the place. The position as regular visitor served afforded a sense of wonder, to photograph/observe what seemed ordinary/part of the taken for granted urban scape to the locals. This made for an informative engagement with locals encountered as they have never observed the city I was documenting with photographs. Lately, the outsider's view has been waning as the city becomes more familiar and chance encounters become somewhat regular.

Although the above-mentioned scholars have brought much-needed insight by drawing attention to neglected areas and aspects of city-life, they enlighten inasmuch as they are silent on equally important elements. For example, in African cities, the figure of the migrant and the maid/helper, the nurse, the sex worker, the banker, the drug dealer and the junkie; the mechanic, the returnee; the student; and the homeless and hustler come to mind.

The chance encounter is a phrase used to describe unscripted, unanticipated, and spontaneous interactions. There was no script/questionnaire/targeted group/representative samples envisaged. The generalizability of some of the findings are attributed to similarities that Kumasi share with similar cities in the continent having to do largely with the colonial legacy (buildings and infrastructure) and impact of economic global on such cities. Kumasi also share a common element in the form of dual-governance system, traditional and modern, that obtains in parts of South Africa in areas are traditional authority. This poses unique challenges for planning intervention through trying to reconcile role of chiefs in land allocations

Chance encounters with locals also yielded invaluable insights about the workings of the city. For example, the extent to which religion and/or a conservative undercurrent informs and permeates much of (urban) life and society is not so readily apparent. Since cash is king in Kumasi city, other forms of collateral have emerged, part of the invisible infrastructure that supports city-life much like roads, bridges, and the like. Here the term is used to refer to interpersonal networks that facilitate life in the city among the poor, including religion. Legend has it that some traders leave goods overnight on tables along the road because the owner might cast a spell on the thief. Such is one of the unique elements encountered.

Another example is that as part of a motivation for a loan application at Savings and Loan's Bank, it is common for loan officers to make references to god and also to refer to the applicant as god-fearing as part of a motivation to guarantee that the loan would be repaid. In the following sections, this theme of encounter informs the discussion and arguments presented.

4. URBAN SPECTACLE AND CONSUMERISM

The first Kumasi Mall at Asokwa Interchange opened to much fanfare in April 2017 in the media. The entire citizenry of Kumasi descended on this piece of prime real estate for what seems like a fleeting moment of the urban spectacle that seems to characterize much of private sector-led projects in cities nowadays.

Thanks to economic globalization, cities like Kumasi are not immune to the entangling web of the world economy and as such present what Murray (2008/9) regards as `predatory investment` opportunities for capital in search of new markets for goods and services. Private-sector investments like shopping atria form part of the shopping list for aspiring `world class` cities including airports, convention centers, and that unwelcome seemingly invisible marauding crowds of the poor and working class.

The triumph of (economic) liberalism, with its emphasis on individual choice, entrepreneurial initiative and private ownership has marked a decisive ideological and socio-cultural shift that has relegated considerations of social justice to the back burner of urban politics (Murray, 2008: 228). In Kumasi and elsewhere, municipal authorities have joined the bandwagon of a market-driven urban development, embracing an entrepreneurial approach to city building. This kind of market-led development has triggered powerful centripetal forces of exclusion, social polarization, marginalization, and has rendered the poor invisible. Such is the nature of entrepreneurial urbanism, which subsumes the right to the city under the rational calculus of

market competition (Murray 2008:4), aided in no less measure by advertising billboards. With almost non-existence of formal employment opportunities, the vast majority is driven to the informal sector economy mainly trading in Chinese manufactured goods.

It seems everyone is selling and everything is for sale in Kumasi. The din emanating from ubiquitous throngs of traders/sellers, the barrage of hooting cars stuck in traffic, and blaring mixture of highlife and gospel music provide a unique soundtrack to this urban spectacle. A unique phenomenon of women balancing what seems like oversized washbasins on their heads who act as human shopping carts provide an essential supporting act. Pavements, which are rare, have become an extension of shops, which makes for an uncomfortable and precarious pedestrian movement. The combinations of all these elements seem to choke the life out of the already convulsing CBD whose majority of colonial period buildings are in desperate need of repair. The relentless heat that pervades the atmosphere creates a mood of bothered and frenetic shopping experience, while also presenting an opportunity for water-sellers to sell to passengers stuck in constant traffic. In spite of it all, there seems to be a method to this madness that eludes the first-time visitor. It is business as usual for the locals.

There is also a thriving second hand market for all types of goods including clothes electronics (stoves, fridges, television sets) on and along the main streets. This serves as an awkward reminder to the reality of the reach, exploitative, and predatory nature of the global economy into cities like Kumasi which are entangled albeit as dumping sites for desuetude and disused goods. Cities like Kumasi have also become critical sites and markets for the production of innovation, goods, and services too as Murray (2008) points out. They are also at the forefront of globalizing modernity as evidenced by flexibility, discontinuity, and seemingly lack of public-sector intervention.

This is an African city in the process of being reclaimed and rebuild simultaneously from the ruins of the colonial city, brick by brick, largely through African ingenuity, and foreign mainly Lebanese finance. Innovation and improvisation are essential components of this city- building and survival. Witness the endless rows of shipping container-sized shopping cubicles lining the street overflow selling Chinese trinkets; repackaging of water into miniature water sachets; mobile Nescafe cart; an outdoor baking factory; the open storm- water channels right next to carriageways, there are no pavements worth mentioning; the meandering alleyways that serve as connections between buildings but also mark a transition from busy streets in front to tranquil living spaces including outdoor dining outlets and the admittedly rare brothel cubicles neatly tucked away in plain sight.

Religion is not outdone by all this and forms part of the spectacle. The gospel of wealth and financial success galore on advertising billboards proselytizing miracles, supernatural, and divine intervention for success in personal and business affairs make for interesting reading in around traffic circles. Commodification has no bounds. Market forces have indeed penetrated all aspects of life. Most lands including the CBD are vested in the hands of the King and administered through long-term leases is increasingly becoming inaccessible, in part, as a result of the practice of upfront rent payments for the duration of the lease. Cash is also king in this city. This has resulted in an urban fabric that is a patchwork of dilapidated and new buildings,

which coincide with leases that are about to expire and newly signed ones. Urban governance takes the form of a unique public-private partnership that involves the institution of the King. Urban governments are expected to create an ‘enabling environment’ and be facilitators rather than direct providers (Lindell, 2008).

5. THE COINCIDENCE OF CONSUMERISM AND ADVERTISING

Kumasi is indeed peppered with texts and colors. Advertising billboards line the main streets leading into and out of the city and concentrated mainly around traffic circles. Individual homes and buildings are not immune to this seemingly ubiquitous phenomenon of advertising for products and services. It is therefore common-place for building structures, including homes, to be emblazoned with colors and logos of particular products and fashionable brands like MTN, Vodacom, and Tigo for example. Mini-vans also serve as mobile advertising spaces. It would appear as if no surface and space seem out of reach for the proselytizing of goods and services as the phenomenon of buying and selling (commodification) penetrates deeper into everyday life and spaces. The message is reinforced in the CBD that is awash with products from elsewhere. The rise in media culture facilitates and animates the process of commodification with its instant messaging. The opening of the first Kumasi shopping mall was sensationalized in large part through social media. Efforts at imposing a univocal vision of consumerism through advertising billboards on such are never frictionless undertakings with uncontested outcomes. Projecting an exclusionary vision is always mirrored in the simultaneous albeit less visible alternate view. Advertising billboards represent a forum for a segment of Kumasi society to speak to and for itself.

There seems to be a reluctance to come to terms with the existing complexity – the messy and disorderly city that defies summation and categorization—in favor of a single market- vision that espouses consumerism and a penchant for the urban spectacle. The following section discusses how commodification manifests itself in the city.

6. INDIFFERENT AND EXCLUSIONARY URBANISM: DELHI (INDIA) AND KIGALI (RWANDA)

All cities lead what amounts to an unsettling double life (Murray 2008:14). ‘By utilizing urban space in ways that facilitates their immediate survival needs, the urban poor have transformed the cityscape – not through a significant alteration of the physical environment but through a redefinition of it. This is the nature of indifferent urbanism that seems less responsive to the needs of the majority of urban poor whose lives depend on a precarious informal sector. The lack of formal and regular work, public/affordable/low-cost housing, and social security for ordinary people provokes increased demands for the ‘right to the city’, which is increasingly contingent on one’s ability to consume services. The necessary services and infrastructure to survive is made possible through collective efforts as people depend on one another to make ends meet (Lindell 2008, Simone 2008). For Simone (2008), African cities survive through a conjunction of heterogeneous activities brought to bear on and elaborated through flexibly configured spaces. He cites a similar scene at a transport depot in Abidjan, which I also

encountered recently at a bus terminal in downtown Kumasi around 1am. This is worth quoting in full:

For example, the transport depot in Abidjan is full of hundreds of young men who function as steerers, baggage loaders, ticket salespeople, hawkers, drivers, gas pumpers, and mechanics. There are constantly shifting connections among them. Each boy who steers passengers to a particular company makes a rapid assessment of their wealth, personal characteristics, and the reason for their journey. This reading determines where the steerer will guide the prospective passengers, who will sell their tickets, who will load their baggage, who will seat them, and so forth. It is as if this collaboration were assembled to maximize the efficiency of each passenger, even though there are no explicit rules or formal means of payment to the steerers. Although each boy gives up control of the passenger to the next player down the line, their collaboration based not on the boys adhering to specific rules but on their capacity to improvise (Simone 2008:71)

This is what he refers to as the `invisible infrastructure` that makes life possible for a majority of inhabitants in African cities. Left to their own devices, people develop innovative means for survival. Such practices remain hidden and often far from academic gaze and popular representations of city-life. Such practices remain hidden and often far from academic gaze and popular re-presentations of city-life. Such practices are too complex and fluid to fashion a cityscape that conforms to prevailing and popular sensibilities and tastes. The urge to eliminate ambiguity, indeterminacy, and uncertainty in urban space is an ingrained habit of city building (Murray 2008). In India Ghertner (2017) discusses about decorative posters that residents hang on their walls and the stories of city and self they convey through them, how residents of a slum have begun to adopt world-class aesthetics as a basis for both locating themselves in the changing city and for framing their own world class aspirations. This was in response to officials and politicians in Delhi who begun to articulate the goal of turning Delhi into a “slum free city”, giving it a “world-class” look.....converting the “under-utilized” public land occupied by slum-dwellers into commercially exploitable private property, Ghertner argues. `Through the court established the presence of slums as the clearest obstacle to Delhi becoming a clean, showpiece, or world-class, city (Ghaertner 2017:207).

In Kigali, Fin (2017) argues that in the pursuit for `exclusive urban aspirations`, Rwanda’s urban policies are set out of the reach of its youthful population—who, in turn, are forced to `chase` after the city’s vision of development. The paper discusses the clash between the contemporary rendering of the city in Kigali and young Rwandans engaged in the informal economy who are not seen as constitutive of Kigali’s modern development. `The city is moving faster than the people – we are chasing, chasing, chasing` according to one interviewee in Fin (2017). Young people find themselves feeling left behind and silenced by the Rwandan state.

Rwanda’s `open moment` has created the opportunity for the government to implement a new vision within its capital city. While this has meant impressive infrastructural development, it has also resulted in the implementation of a rigid and restrictive social, economic, and political engineering project. A `new` beginning and the construction of Rwanda, both materially and in narrative, have not meant that its population has had equal opportunities (Fin 2017:13)

7. READING AFRICAN KUMASI

India and Rwanda seem to have taken a step further in reference to Kumasi as the Garden City is part of a recurring theme of selective self-referential. The urban landscape consists not only of a built environment subject to radical alteration and modification but also of a constellation of outward signs that convey a host of overlapping, intersecting, and sometimes conflicting meanings (Murray 2008). It would seem that there is an ongoing struggle, perhaps outright denial, subconsciously even, to come to terms with the complexities of the city-images on the ground coupled with a lack of means for re-presenting such diversity. Stripped-down public spaces are forced with an increasingly dispassionate narrow-mindedness into the exclusive role of conduits for the uninterrupted flow of vehicles and the dumping ground for the urban poor (Murray 2008:29).

City-building oscillate between creative interventions, the fashioning of something new that never existed before, on the one side, and the selective destruction, erasure, and elimination on the other. Billboards present, inasmuch as they supplant another vision and image of the city. Reference to Kumasi as a Garden City after the famous by Ebenezer Howard, an allusion to her colonial past, was yet another predominant vision of the city that was partially realized if at all. The city is the seat of Ashanti Kingdom, a theatre of class and ethnic antagonism among the Ashanti, Ewes, northerners (largely Muslim) who inhabit different parts of the city.

The unintended use of urban space always operates in tandem with the official of orderly cityscape, which constitutes a formidable social force in its own right against the officially sanctioned prerogatives of the powerful and privileged (Murray 2008:14). Beneath the billboards a different image emerges, not so much as a counter-representation to images displayed on billboards above, but as opportunistic spaces to capitalize on the passing gaze for a quick sale. From my observation as a Town Planner, I hypothesize as follows:

- The growth of cities can be spontaneous such that there are limits to planning as planning can go against spontaneity.
- It is the town planning rules, standards, norms and laws that can encumber spontaneity in the name of order and decorum;
- The growth of cities can therefore be organic (spontaneous) and non-organic (when planning is involved)
- As such, the growth of cities can span between the organic and non-organic, and everything in between.
- The influences on the growth of cities can both be internal and external – the internal ones include the spirit of entrepreneurship among the populace, and the location of the billboards; and external may include the Chinese and other influences.
- Growth can be accompanied by decay (ruins) calling for renewal and further renewal;
- In a state of flux, the city goes into a state of hyper-commodification in which almost everything is for sale from the spaces where the billboard stands to what is displayed on them, to the goods and products on the market stalls which are all commodified.

8. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The social fabric of the cityscape itself – that is, its movements towards growth and decline, its juxtaposition of planning and improvisation, its balance between private luxury and public amenities, and the availability of shared spaces and the resources of collective consumption – sets the limits and possibilities for the realization of a decent urban life (Murray 2011:236). The view being expressed is that the physical features of the cityscape are saturated with meaning and symbolism where collective memories and imagined futures are inscribed in the built environment (Murray 2008:5).

What is needed is the critical work on the present that is tied to an inclusionary re- presentation of Kumasi. After-all, the city is a vast canvass that is capable of accommodating a diversity of narratives. Kumasi is still trying to define herself. Something is in the process of being made. The city is being summoned into being for all to see besides the billboards.

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